

USING INTERACTIVE AND NON-STANDARD TEACHING METHODS TO INCREASE THE EFFECTIVENESS OF LANGUAGE LEARNING

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Abstract. *Some pedagogical methods of interactive teaching models and methods of teaching languages which are used at the English lessons are considered in the article. The article is suggested some exercises which help to get to know members of the group closely and to establish inherent group communications for the effective learning and vocabulary activities. For the purpose of developing creative specialists' ability are provided using communication possibilities in the teaching process on the professional basis.*

Keywords: *Interactive methods, presentation, computer training, group discussion, business and role play, quiz, different classroom activities, try to find answer, choose the correct answer.*

Introduction

The 21st century is an age of rapid information and communication development, technological progress and market relations. To feel "comfortable" in this "space," future specialists need not only to acquire a specific volume of professional knowledge and skills but also to develop and enhance their speech and thinking skills for communication, particularly in a professional context, with a team. Alongside political issues, language problems are no less relevant today. Recently, there has been significant interest in educational models, pedagogical innovations, technologies, and methods that prove to be the most effective for this purpose. Questions about the organization and intensification of the educational process are constantly in the spotlight. How can we provide the necessary amount of information in the least amount of time? How can we ensure deep understanding? Since foreign language teaching is a specific instance of education as a whole, answers to these and many other questions can be found in the underlying methodology.

In the current conditions of educational service market development and the demands of the information technology era, teaching in English should combine established directive practices with a modern, innovative, and interactive learning model. It is essential to remember that learners must be ready to consciously use the language in real-life communication situations. By "consciousness," we refer to a principle of communicative linguistics through which learners acquire knowledge of facts, definitions, and laws, comprehend conclusions and generalizations, express their thoughts correctly in speech, and independently apply their knowledge in practice.

There is no doubt that organizing such education for non-philology students, who have a modest number of hours allocated for foreign language study at university, can be quite challenging. Therefore, the communicative goal of education must be clearly defined: why do we speak or write? The process of information transfer is based on the principle of interaction between the teacher and the student. It requires greater activity from the learner and their creative rethinking of the information received. It is advisable to use some non-traditional methods of conducting lessons, incorporating poems and riddles, songs and charades, rebuses

and crosswords, as well as tests. All the aforementioned points, as practice shows, are highly effective in enriching students' vocabulary.

In classes focused on developing oral speech, the following problematic situations are interesting: relationships between children and parents, friendships, money issues, norms of behavior in society, the role of technical progress, youth problems, politics, economics, etc. Interactive game lessons offered for communicative language study involve exercises categorized into seven sections based on their objectives: exercises to create an atmosphere for group work; exercises to identify common interests; exercises that support group coherence; linking exercises; stimulating exercises; exercises that encourage creativity; and concluding exercises.

Here are some exercises on the topic: "***Environmental Pollution.***"

Task I. Vocabulary Match. Objective: Enhance vocabulary related to environmental pollution. Instructions: Match the terms with their correct definitions.

Pollutant

Ecosystem

Biodegradable

Greenhouse gases

Acid rain

Sustainability

Definitions:

a. A gas that contributes to the greenhouse effect by absorbing infrared radiation.

b. A substance that contaminates the environment.

c. Rain that has been acidified by pollutants, leading to environmental harm.

d. Capable of being decomposed by biological processes.

e. A community of living organisms and their physical environment interacting as a system.

f. The ability to be maintained at a certain rate or level without depleting resources.

Answers: 1-b, 2-e, 3-d, 4-a, 5-c, 6-f

Task II. Discussion Questions. Objective: Encourage critical thinking and discussion about environmental pollution. Instructions: Discuss the following questions in pairs or small groups.

1. What are the main sources of environmental pollution in your community?

2. How does pollution affect human health and wildlife?

3. What measures can individuals take to reduce their carbon footprint?

4. Discuss the role of governments and organizations in combating environmental pollution.

5. Can you think of any successful initiatives that have reduced pollution in your area or globally?

Task III. Choose the correct answer. Learner A asks a question and Learner B answers it.

A: 1. Why is pollution very important problem now?

B: a) *Because, air, water and soil are necessary for existence of all living things, but polluted air can cause illness, and even death.*

b) *People lived in uncrowded rural areas and did not have pollution — causing machines.*

A: 2. Can food on polluted soil, be grown?

B: a) *Yes, it can.*

b) *No, it cannot.*

A: 3. What are the problems with automobiles and industrial enterprises connected with environmental pollution?

B: a) *Automobiles are polluting the air but they provide transportation for the people. Factories pollute the air and the water but they provide jobs for people and produce goods.*

b) *We need automobiles and factories polluting environment*

Task IV. Add the missing parts of the sentences from the text and complete the sentences below with the words

1. Air, ... and ... are necessary for existence of all living things

2. Environmental ... spoils the natural beauty of our planet.

3. Fertilizers and pesticides are important for growing crops but they can ruin...

4. Scientists and engineers can find the ways ... pollution from automobiles and factories.

a) *soil*

b) *to reduce pollution from automobiles and factories*

c) *water, soil*

d) *pollution*

Check your answers below (see example)

1	2	3	4
c	d	a	b

Home assignment: Research and Presentation

Objective: *Develop research and presentation skills.*

Instructions: *Choose one type of environmental pollution (air, water, soil, noise, etc.) and prepare a short presentation (5-10 minutes) covering the following points:*

Definition and causes of the chosen type of pollution.

Effects on the environment and human health.

Case studies or examples of areas affected by this type of pollution.

Solutions or strategies to mitigate this type of pollution.

Your personal opinion on what actions should be taken.

These exercises help group members get to know each other better, set the tone for group work, quickly establish intra-group relationships and norms of behavior, stimulate and encourage collaboration, and provide new perspectives on the world by applying new, unconventional methods. (Games and Warm-ups: A Guide for Group Work. Based on the Warmups guide prepared by Nell Warren Associates Inc.) Educational games make the process of learning a foreign language more interesting and engaging. A sense of equality and an atmosphere of enthusiasm allow students to overcome shyness, stiffness, language barriers, and fatigue. Through games, for example, pronunciation can be practiced effectively, vocabulary and grammar can be activated, and not only listening skills but also the art of speaking can be developed.

However, when using games in lessons, educators need to constantly keep in mind several important points:

1. The choice of game format should be pedagogically and didactically thought out and justified; it should involve as many learners as possible.

2. The game should match the language abilities of the learners.

3. Language games should be conducted exclusively in the foreign language.

4. The teacher should remember that games are not a substitute for systematic study and intensive training.

5. Games should be used in a measured, appropriate and planned way, bearing in mind that they build on material already learnt.

Performing in the classroom is the strongest motivator for learning a language, it helps to create a natural language environment. For example, the use of theatrical games in lessons has proven effective, primarily for developing skills and abilities in preparatory oral speech. Students in colleges or universities, especially in the early stages of learning, are also keen on the opportunity to try their hand at acting. In modern practice, active learning methods are becoming increasingly common: training sessions, programmed and computer-based learning, group discussions, analysis of specific practical situations, and business and role-playing games.

There are also so-called non-standard lessons, such as press conference lessons, conference lessons, birthday lessons, spinning lessons, and matchmaking lessons. It is advisable to conduct these in advanced classes or student groups, as they require significant preparatory work from both the teacher and the students themselves. In this context, the strategy for verbal interaction is defined by the communicative goals of the participants, such as: requesting, obtaining, or conveying significant information; discussing an issue in order to make a decision; convincing a partner of something; proving the correctness of one's position; evaluating a fact, situation, or object; expressing or defending one's opinion; supporting or refuting a partner's opinion; proposing and justifying a hypothesis; indicating a way to solve a problem; stating a fact; summarizing; making a conclusion; supporting an idea; expressing doubts or criticism regarding the discussed issue; telling about an event, person, object, etc.

Teaching a foreign language based on interactive methods fosters team cohesion, promotes sociability, creates a favorable psychological climate in the learning group, and ensures a solid grasp of knowledge. The process and results of learning gain personal significance for all participants and allow learners to develop the ability to solve problems independently. Time moves forward, new technologies enter our lives, and therefore, resting on one's laurels means losing much. Utilizing the resources of a computer lab or university classroom for foreign language lessons is a powerful motivator that must be leveraged in teaching practice.

In conclusion, it is important to note that foreign language lessons provide educators with significant opportunities to spark interest and create motivation for further study. The importance of learning a foreign language today cannot be overstated. For practicing teachers, there are limitless opportunities for creative exploration of new forms and methods to activate the learning process.

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